

Woodlands for All

A GUIDE TOWARDS FOSTERING COMMUNITY BENEFITS
AND ENGAGEMENT IN COMMUNAL WOODLANDS

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Foreword

Communities increasingly take charge of their wellbeing, with a notable shift towards local empowerment. This guideline was co-developed to illustrate the interrelations between the community and nature. At a time when we are globally facing the loss of natural ecosystems, the sustainable management of woodlands and communities' participation has never been more important.

This guide compiles insights from a literature review on community woodland initiatives, emphasising their benefits and strategies to enhance their positive impact on human well-being and the environment. This research project is part of the COEVOLVERS (Coevolutionary approach to unlock the transformative potential of nature-based solutions for more inclusive and resilient communities), a Horizon Europe-funded project (2022 – 2026).

This guide presents practical ideas for community groups to explore and enhance their woodland spaces. Our interest is to help inform key stakeholders who use woodlands frequently. We understand that woodlands may not appeal to everyone; however, we intend to create a document that enhances accessibility and usability for a diverse audience, including schools, community groups, environmental professionals, and policymakers. We hope it can inform future woodland management practices and inspire deeper collaboration between communities and those involved in the stewardship of our natural landscapes. For updates on this guide, feel free to visit www.woodlandsforall.co.uk

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The guide is informed by our research interactions with the Murray Park Trust and the Alford community regarding the significance of community-owned woodlands. We thank the James Hutton Institute team involved in this project. Your contributions and support were important in achieving the results of this guide. Your contributions were invaluable, and we sincerely hope this guideline serves as a tool to inspire and facilitate positive change, supporting the growth and stewardship of woodlands in the UK and across Europe. We believe these efforts could sustain the natural world's future green infrastructure projects.

We would also like to extend our heartfelt thanks to the [COEVOLVERS](#) project for its support. The guidelines are grounded in the principles of the coevolutionary process, which emphasises the interconnected development of human and natural systems. By integrating ecological, social, and economic dimensions, this guideline hopes to contribute to tackling and positively impacting the environmental degradation of our times.

Finally, we would like to express our appreciation for the financial support from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, without which this project would not have been possible.

Who is this guide for?

This guide aims to serve as an engaging and [interactive resource](#) for community groups, fostering collective woodland stewardship and encouraging active local participation. While numerous reports and guides are tailored for professionals and experts in this field, resources specifically designed for non-experts, such as community groups, local initiatives, and schools, are comparatively scarce. These groups often seek accessible guidance on how to engage with and benefit from community woodlands. [Schools](#) and [educators](#) can use it to create outdoor classrooms that cultivate early connections with nature while environmental practitioners gain practical insights into nature-based project implementation. The guide aims to provide [community space coordinators](#) with tools to foster inclusive and sustainable woodland management, enabling them to effectively navigate and address the socio-ecological complexities inherent in community woodlands. [Tourism](#) and [cultural heritage professionals](#) are also guided on leveraging woodlands for sustainable tourism and cultural preservation.

Please note that woodlands can differ significantly in their level of ecosystem functionality, which plays a crucial role in determining their capacity to provide community benefits.

Using photo interactive links in this guide

This guide provides places and points to explore Scotland's woodlands with the [What3words](#) app. What3words is a geolocation system that divides the world into a grid of 3m x 3m squares, with each square assigned a unique combination of three words.

Some photos in this guide are marked with icon, which points to a [what3words](#) reference. You can visit these locations using the what3words mobile app. The three words act as an exact address, making it easy to pinpoint locations anywhere in the world. For example, in the above photo, the **BENCH** in a woodland in Scotland can be located using just three words [polishing.decrease.about](#) (57.238553N, -2.698506W); the **PATH** is [prude.walking.twitching](#) (57.238521N, -2.698422W). This system simplifies sharing and remembering locations with words instead of using long, complicated GPS coordinates. For more information, the service is available through the [what3words mobile app](#) and website www.what3words.com

In this guide, QR codes are active weblinks to websites or geolocations. The links are only available when the guide is in PDF format. Additional valuable resources and website links are provided at the end of this guide.

Please note that the links provided in this guide will direct you to external websites. Over time, these links may become outdated or subject to change.

Preserving nature is important for our wellbeing

The natural world provides us with **countless resources**, from clean air and water to fertile soil and biodiversity, which are all important for survival and wellbeing. However, these **benefits can only be sustained if the ecosystems provide them with the means to thrive**. When nature is disrupted or degraded, its ability to support life diminishes, impacting the environment and, consequently, humans.

Nature's resources are often referred to as ecosystem services. These benefits are ecosystems' direct and indirect contributions to human wellbeing and quality of life. These ecosystem services are typically categorised into four broad services:

1. **Supporting services** are the foundation of ecosystems. They include photosynthesis, nutrient cycling, and pollination. They make it possible for all life to exist.
2. **Provisioning services** can be extracted or harvested from nature. For example, nuts, berries and mushrooms are all direct products of ecosystems.
3. **Regulating services** moderate natural occurrences in ecosystems and ensure the ongoing sustainable functionality of these systems. For example, plants clean and filter water and regulate climate.
4. **Cultural services** are non-material benefits, such as hiking, swimming, and camping, that enhance human physical, mental, and emotional health.

These ecosystem services serve as the foundation for delivering community benefits through woodlands.

Community benefits as part of nature-based solutions

Nature-based solutions are actions or strategies that use natural processes and ecosystems to **solve environmental, social and economic challenges**. Think of them as ways to work with nature, rather than against it, to address problems like water management and biodiversity loss. Nature-based solutions leverage the power of nature to tackle problems cost-effectively and sustainably. They respond to issues and have other advantages by improving biodiversity and people's wellbeing and enhancing the capacity to **withstand the impacts of climate change**.

RECIPROCAL CARE: Nature and humans

Mutual respect and reciprocity between humans and nature are vital for maintaining a balanced and sustainable relationship with the environment. By caring for nature, we help preserve ecosystems that supply essential resources such as clean air, water, and fertile soil—resources that are fundamental to our survival and well-being.

The growing number of nature-based solutions initiatives indicates a promising potential for **enhanced benefits at the community level** in the future. For example, by restoring ecosystems, practising sustainable agriculture, increasing biodiversity, and planting trees, communities can be more resilient to climate change and food insecurity and create sustainable livelihoods. Involving communities in such projects creates a sense of belonging, builds social connections, and increases the sharing of knowledge and skills, enhancing the viability of the projects.

Community's shared goals and interests

"Community is a group of people with diverse characteristics who are linked by social ties, share common perspectives, and engage in joint action in geographical locations or settings." ¹ This sense of connection fosters an impression of belonging and shared responsibility, such as in community-managed woodlands, where members collaboratively care for and manage the resource. Community woodlands, particularly those near residential areas, are conveniently accessible. These areas **promote learning** and community identity through participatory projects and **hands-on activities** like tree planting and wildlife observation. Community woodlands improve wellbeing by offering spaces for relaxation and connection with nature. They **also have the potential to foster social cohesion and community pride**, e.g. through tree planting and environmental workshops. At the same time, nature and social processes play a beneficial role in supporting wellbeing. This guide provides a resource for exploring the following 19 key community benefits derived from community woodlands.

¹ MacQueen, K. M., McLellan, E., Metzger, D. S., Kegeles, S., Strauss, R. P., Scotti, R., Blanchard, L., & Trotter, R. T. (2001). What is community? An evidence-based definition for participatory public health. *American Journal of Public Health*, 91(12), 1929–1938.

PART 1: HEALTH AND HAPPINESS

Health and happiness are deeply intertwined with our connection to nature. Creating spaces that allow people to **slow down and immerse** themselves in the natural world fosters not only physical health but also mental and spiritual wellbeing.

The environment offers a chance to relax and think about life in the bigger picture by taking our eyes off the stressors of work and family life. Such settings provide calm and restore energy, allowing people to lead fulfilling lives and balance their bodies, minds, and spirits.

1 Enabling places for connecting with nature

Nature awareness is about understanding and appreciating the natural world, recognising its value, and building a meaningful connection. Such awareness is highly beneficial for promoting environmental stewardship and enhancing psychological wellbeing. It's essential to create environments that both adults and children can inhabit. Interacting with nature benefits the emotional and cognitive development of individuals. It's important to create spaces that both adults and children can enjoy. Being in nature helps with emotional and cognitive development. These spaces encourage curiosity, play, and learning, helping children, teenagers and adults explore and appreciate the beauty of the natural world. Moreover, when people of all ages are given the opportunity to connect with nature, it **fosters a sense of belonging**. By offering these opportunities, we help cultivate future environmental stewards who recognise the vital role of protecting the natural world for future generations.

In addition to fostering individual growth, these natural spaces **encourage community connections**, creating environments where individuals can share their experiences and knowledge. The more people engage with nature, the more likely they are to **advocate for its protection**, ensuring the preservation of these **green spaces** (natural or semi-natural areas that provide ecological, social, and recreational benefits by integrating vegetation, open spaces, and biodiversity into human environments).

IN FOCUS:

Above is a play area located in Aberdeen, Scotland, designed to immerse children in a natural forest setting. This nature-based play space nurtures **environmental awareness** and respect for the natural world, **fostering a deep connection** with nature from a young age.

 Explore this child-friendly space in detail with our interactive 360° photo.

2 Enabling places that promote relaxation

Nurturing the bond between self and nature is beneficial to everyone, especially those who live a fast-paced lifestyle. **Nature's slower pace teaches us to be present, mindful and more attuned** to the essential aspects of our wellbeing. Features that can help us to slow down in community woodlands include pavilions, seating areas, water features, picnic areas, and paths that offer variety and changing scenery.

IN FOCUS:
 The **thoughtfully designed seating areas** serve as intentional invitations for visitors to **pause and connect with their surroundings**. Carefully placed to maximise comfort and visual appeal, these places encourage visitors to slow their pace, take a break from their journey, and **immerse themselves** in natural beauty. Some seating areas are tucked beneath the cool, protective shade of trees, offering a peaceful refuge on warm days, while others are positioned to provide panoramic views of the woodlands.

Forest at Bennachie, Inverurie

Allan Park, Aberdeen

Picnic spot at Bennachie Forests

Murray Park, Alford

3 Health and wellbeing

Green spaces, clean air, and bird sounds in woodlands have many therapeutic benefits. Together, these features create an atmosphere that **provides relaxation and recovery**.

Walking in woodlands benefits mental health by reducing stress and anxiety through the calming influence of nature. The natural environment of a woodland helps promote relaxation and mental clarity. Immersing oneself in a woodland **enhances mood** and provides a natural boost to overall emotional wellbeing. Natural rhythms often mimic **white noise**, which helps enhance focus or mindfulness. The soothing sounds of nature help calm the mind, promote relaxation, reduce stress, and improve focus.

How does listening to running water make you feel?

Forest therapy, also known as forest bathing, is a therapeutic practice that involves immersing oneself in a natural forest environment to promote mental and physical wellbeing.

Green prescribing supports people in engaging in nature-based interventions and activities to improve their mental and physical health. For more details, visit [[Green Social Prescribing](#)²]

DID YOU KNOW ?

Bird and water sounds in a forest create a calming environment that helps reduce stress and anxiety and promote mental well-being.

Listening to the sound of **running water**, such as rivers or waterfalls, has been shown to have significant therapeutic effects. The consistent, soothing sounds can induce relaxation by **reducing stress and anxiety** levels, promoting a sense of calm and tranquility.

Scan the QR code to immerse yourself in the soothing sounds of running water.

²NHS England » Green social prescribing, Nhs.uk. Available at: <https://www.england.nhs.uk/personalisedcare/social-prescribing/green-social-prescribing/> (Accessed: January 21, 2025)

4 Spiritual wellbeing

Spirituality pertains to connecting with a power or transcendent presence that one perceives as being outside of or more significant than oneself², and that intuitively offers a deeper and more meaningful understanding of the universe than mere intellectual cognition. Being surrounded by trees, plants and wildlife can foster a sense of wonder and reverence, reminding participants of the **interconnectedness of life**. Woodlands offer a serene environment for spiritual contemplation where individuals can connect with nature, cultivating spiritual awareness and omniscient consciousness.

 pursuit.laugh.replace

Cothiemuir Forest Stone Circle

IN FOCUS:

During the 2019 COVID epidemic, a church congregation in Alford, Scotland, gathered in a nearby park for fellowship. The open-air setting provided a safe environment for meetings and created a serene venue for prayer.

Tree stump seating for a group of people

DID YOU KNOW ?

Coming together in nature fosters a sense of community beyond human connections, including all living beings. This broader sense of fellowship can cultivate a more inclusive and expansive experience.

Stone circles are often regarded as sacred sites with spiritual significance, believed to be ancient places for ritual. For some, this can facilitate **a sense of groundedness** and connection to something beyond and more significant than oneself.

³Elkins, D. N., Hedstrom, L. J., Hughes, L. L., Leaf, J. A., & Saunders, C. (1988). Toward a humanistic-phenomenological spirituality: Definition, description, and measurement. *Journal of Humanistic Psychology*, 28

5 Recreation

Enjoying the outdoors and being active has become increasingly important as urban sprawl continues to take over. Expanses of concrete buildings and asphalt roads encroach on natural spaces. Woodlands provide various recreational opportunities, such as **hiking, birdwatching, cycling, running, camping,** and **nature observation.**

These opportunities are in demand as urban areas expand and human affluence rises. They offer **relief from the stresses of urban life.** **Dog walking** supports recreation by providing a fun and active way to exercise while physically enjoying the outdoors. It also offers mental relaxation and an opportunity for social interaction, benefitting the dog and the owner.

Birdwatching is an excellent recreational activity. Scan the QR code to listen to local bird songs.

DID YOU KNOW ?

Mobile apps can enhance woodland recreation by providing digital guides, interactive maps, and wildlife identification tools, making outdoor exploration more engaging. These apps allow users to navigate trails, **learn about local flora and fauna,** and participate in activities like geocaching or birdwatching. They also promote sustainable behaviours by encouraging responsible tourism and supporting conservation efforts.

Geocaching

AllTrails

Cyclers

iNaturalist

BirdNET

PictureThis

WWF Forests

Night Sky

PART 2: ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

Integrating green spaces into urban and rural settings is critical as these provide a myriad of ecosystem services. Such ecosystem services include the regulation of microclimate, whereby vegetation aids in regulating temperatures, which results in better living conditions. Green areas also improve air quality by dealing with air pollutants and, at the same time, provide spaces for people to engage with nature, which increases awareness and appreciation. Moreover, natural elements like trees and bushes help minimise noise pollution and improve general health. The visual appreciation of such spaces improves people's living standards, and the availability of clean, well-designed footpaths stimulates the use and active recreation within woodlands.

6 Microclimate regulation

Urban woodlands are essential because they help **regulate microclimates** by providing cooling, shade, improved air quality, and reduced wind turbulence. Green spaces **make people feel more comfortable** by creating cooler microclimates. As temperatures rise, more people will rely on these green spaces for relief ³.

Above, urban residents can visit the park to escape the city heat and enjoy a summer day in a woodland in Stockholm. Urban parks like **Humlegården** are crucial in mitigating Stockholm's urban heat island effect.

⁴ Yuan, Tongfang. "The Role of Green Infrastructure in Mitigating the Urban Heat Island Effect." Open Journal of Applied Sciences 14.11 (2024): 3155-3164.

People enjoy clean air because it offers a range of physical and mental benefits. Fresh air is rich in **oxygen**, enhancing overall body oxygenation and improving energy levels and health. Urbanisation has led to a growing understanding that air quality changes are among the challenges of urban pollution that must be tackled. Besides the harmful health effects of air pollution, increased pollutants like carbon dioxide contribute to the greenhouse effect and rising temperatures. Consequently, **maintaining air quality in woodlands is essential** for regulating ecosystem services.

Click this link to immerse yourself in the fresh, early morning woodland air captured in this 360° photo

Woodlands are important in maintaining clean air in cities by acting as **natural air purifiers**. Trees absorb pollutants such as nitrogen dioxide, sulphur dioxide and carbon monoxide from the atmosphere, improving overall air quality. Urban woodlands also improve city ventilation by **regulating airflow, dust and wind turbulence**.

8 Nature accessibility

Woodland access **offers a view of woodland nature**, which is essential for everyone, including those with mobility challenges, visual impairments, and sensory or processing disabilities. For these individuals, having accessible natural spaces such as urban woodlands with wheelchair-friendly paths or easily reachable green areas becomes essential to their wellbeing. It allows them to experience nature's mental and physical health benefits like others.

Parking spaces near the entrance provide convenient access for wheelchair users, ensuring easy entry to paths and access. Take a closer look at this designated parking area for accessibility features in this 360° photo.

Ensuring that these spaces are designed to offer **access for everyone**, with ramps, benches, and transportation options, helps create equitable access for all. **Clear signage** and **detailed information** about the area's offerings can help community members make informed plans before they visit.

 waltzes.rugs.smaller

Clear signage at Foggieton Reserve

9 Nature awareness

Nature awareness involves understanding and appreciating the natural world, recognising its benefits and cultivating a meaningful connection. **Woodlands foster nature awareness** by offering immersive, accessible environments where communities can experience biodiversity and natural processes firsthand. Here are several ways in which woodlands provide a green space for the community and help contribute to nature awareness:

Providing a variety of woodland habitats:

Woodlands with native tree species, in particular, provide diverse habitats that support thriving ecosystems. Creating spaces where animals can live and move freely fosters a deeper appreciation for these ecosystems and promotes greater awareness of the importance of conservation.

Sensory connection: Walking through woodlands is a rich sensory experience, engaging multiple senses: sight (vibrant autumn leaves), sound (melodic birdsong), smell (earthy aroma of damp soil), and touch (the rough texture of tree bark). This multi-sensory experience can enhance people's connection to the natural world.

Signage creates awareness

Playful badgers captured on a trail camera.
Video courtesy of Helen Rowe

Nature monitoring: Woodlands provide a venue for community involvement in nature-based projects, such as wildlife monitoring and path maintenance. Trail cameras allow people to monitor biodiversity and track species' behaviour by capturing images or videos of animals in their natural habitats. On the left is an example of trail camera footage in a woodland.

Woodlands are great at **lowering noise levels**, but how much they can reduce sound depends on the weather, the type of trees and how the woodlands are cared for. For example, in certain seasons, woodlands with lots of leaves and thick branches can block out more noise, while in other seasons, like winter, they might be less effective because the trees have fewer leaves. The types of trees also matter, as some trees, especially ones with thick leaves or soft bark, are better at absorbing sound than others. The woodland floor also plays a part; soft ground covered in grass, leaves or moss can **absorb sound**, making the **woodland quieter**.

All these factors facilitate the woodland's role as a peaceful environment. The sound of traffic, construction, or other loud and noisy urban settings can be unpleasant, but some people may find solace and peace in the woodlands. The trees, plants, and soil form a shield that protects the community from the harsh sounds of the city. Instead, it allows one to hear soft sounds, such as the wind blowing through the leaves or birds singing.

Trees with **bright colours**, such as Aspen, Lime, and Silver Birch, undergo chlorophyll breakdown, turning their leaves yellow. This seasonal colour change enhances the landscape's **visual diversity**.

A sense of wildness, mystery, and natural beauty often characterises the aesthetics of unmanaged / minimally managed woodlands. These environments feature dense vegetation and fallen trees that create habitat for various wildlife species.

Open forests and paths exude a sense of tranquillity, with sunlight filtering through widely spaced trees onto a clean, mossy forest floor. The clear understory and healthy, towering trees create an airy, spacious feel, inviting quiet exploration.

In the three different woodland examples above, appreciating a woodland means more than just liking how it looks; it's about providing nature awareness and noticing the **sights, sounds, smells** and the **peaceful feeling** that being in a woodland can give us. Unmanaged places are often perceived negatively, as their untidy appearance and apparent lack of order can be associated with neglect rather than being appreciated as a form of natural beauty. **Everyone may find different things to enjoy** in a woodland, depending on where they come from, their cultural values, or even their memories. **People have diverse aesthetic preferences**. Some are drawn to the towering trees and crisp, fresh air, while others find beauty in the raw, untamed wilderness of woodlands.

The pathways shown in the photos provide access to previously inaccessible locations, enhancing mobility and usability for individuals. In the specific case of community woodlands, well-maintained paths and roads enhance the safety and availability of routes for visitors, promoting contact with nature and physical activity.

Developing, protecting and **maintaining trails** ensures that people of **all physical abilities** can enjoy woodlands. These trails are designed to be accessible to everyone, including individuals with mobility challenges, young children, parents with strollers and elderly visitors. By providing safe, easy-to-navigate paths, these trails allow more people to explore and experience nature, regardless of their physical capabilities.

Properly maintained trails are also necessary after heavy rains and poor drainage. They allow visitors to continue accessing the woodland without facing risky or muddy conditions. In doing so, they promote inclusivity and support sustainable woodland management by **encouraging responsible use** of the woodland and helping preserve the natural environment.

PART 3: SOCIAL BENEFITS

Woodlands also provide social benefits which go beyond ecology and the environment. They help foster attachment to place and ownership sentiments among people. The social value of woodlands also reflects their role in promoting justice, equality, and inclusion. They offer safe, shared spaces where individuals from diverse backgrounds can come together, fostering a sense of community and mutual respect. Furthermore, woodlands are associated with cultural and historical aspects that maintain culture and provide a continuous link with the past. They also serve as essential spaces for **education and learning**, inspiring curiosity and fostering a **deeper understanding of nature and sustainability**.

The concept of a *sense of place* reflects an environment's unique character and emotional impact, often called the 'spirit of place.'⁴ It encompasses the **sensory, emotional and cognitive layers of how people experience and relate** to their surroundings. A strong sense of place and attachment often grows with individuals' time in a location, creating a deep-rooted connection to that landscape.

Feeling connected or having a role in managing woodlands may result in developing a greater sense of belonging, which would encourage residents to take on stewardship responsibilities. Such a deep emotional relationship encourages people to use, appreciate, and protect the land through participation in community conservation activities.

Activities such as reforestation through tree planting, organised clean-up campaigns and promoting **biodiversity-friendly practices** contribute to the immediate beautification of local areas and long-term ecological resilience.

Tree planting can future-proof woodlands by ensuring they remain resilient and productive in the face of environmental, ecological, and socio-economic challenges.

Tree planting in Murry Park, Scotland

⁵Relph, Edward. "Place and placelessness." *Pion Limited* 156 (1976).

14 **Social value in justice, equity and inclusion**

This guide centres on inclusivity for humans and non-humans, **highlighting the importance of making woodlands accessible** and **welcoming to everyone**. It envisions a diverse and enriched society where everyone's contributions are recognised and valued. Community woodlands offer unique benefits for marginalised groups, minorities, low-income individuals, people with disabilities, the elderly, and migrants, while everyone can contribute to environmental justice for endangered species. By creating opportunities for social interaction, these spaces foster social cohesion, promote a shared sense of identity, and encourage collective responsibility for conservation. However, heterogeneity among these stakeholders may also introduce different priorities, purposes, and values, sometimes leading to conflicts. Managing these conflicts is essential in ensuring trust, working together, and a feeling of belonging to the community. Open communication and trying to understand the other side's point of view are helpful for the resolution of conflicts, thereby providing access and utility to community woodlands by all members.

<https://virtualtours.hutton.ac.uk/coevolvers/>

The **Virtual Nature Tour** is an innovative tool that allows community members who cannot physically access green spaces to do so. It also helps visitors familiarise themselves with the area before arriving (click the icon below to view the woodland virtual tour).

DID YOU KNOW ?

Social justice and inclusion extend beyond human communities to encompass non-human species that struggle to thrive in their natural habitats. In the case of the red squirrel, a protected species in the UK, conservation efforts reflect this broader understanding of justice.

These small mammals have faced significant challenges due to habitat loss and competition from invasive species like the grey squirrel. To address these issues, the UK has implemented various conservation programs to restore ecosystems where red squirrels can **regain their ecological agency**.

A red squirrel captured on a trail camera. Video courtesy of Helen Rowe

Täby woodlands

IN FOCUS:

On the left is an example of a Bronze Age burial mound in Täby, Sweden. These significant archaeological sites offer insights into early Scandinavian culture and burial practices. **These ancient mounds are protected for their historical value and by preserving surrounding woodlands, which act as natural buffers against modern development.**

By safeguarding these forests, local authorities help maintain the integrity of both the cultural heritage and the ecological environment. This integrated approach ensures that the burial mounds remain undisturbed, allowing future generations to appreciate Sweden's rich prehistoric legacy while **preserving the area's biodiversity.**

Woodland areas can play an **essential role in safeguarding these historic places** by preventing them from storms or being altered by urban development. They act as stewards of cultural heritage, monuments and artefacts for public education and enjoyment. These **landscapes are physical reminders of human history**, offering valuable insights into past societies' lives. They serve as living records of cultural heritage, showcasing the evolution of human activities and ways of life across different periods. Historically, these landscapes are often home to significant events, structures, and monuments that played key roles in **shaping a community's identity**. They help us understand earlier social, political, and economic dynamics. Preserving such areas ensures fostering a sense of continuity and identity.

Preserving these landscapes often brings **socio-economic benefits through tourism, education and community engagement**. They attract visitors interested in history and culture, which can support local businesses and create jobs.

16 Education and learning

 blaze.disprove.drill

Arnhall Moss Nature Reserve, Aberdeen

 waltzes.rugs.smaller

Foggieton Nature Reserve, Aberdeen

 shepherdess.teach.book

Haughton Park, Alford

 tigers.wished.monks

Hazlehead Woodlands, Aberdeen

These four signboards in Scotland's woodlands inform the public about the local ecosystems, showcasing the wildlife and natural features visitors can experience. Beyond providing information, these signs are designed to raise awareness and deepen appreciation for the environment, **guiding the community through the area's diverse and rich biodiversity**. Educational activities in woodlands help raise environmental awareness and encourage sustainable living for people of all ages.

An important part of "**woodland education**" is its role in teaching children about woodland ecosystems while fostering a deep appreciation and sense of responsibility for the environment from a young age. By teaching our young stakeholders about ecosystems and nature-based solutions, we can help them understand how these solutions support healthier ecosystems and contribute to **biodiversity conservation** worldwide.

PART 4: ECONOMIC BENEFITS

Woodlands play a critical role in supporting local economies through various interconnected activities. Their contribution spans food provisioning, recreation, tourism and sustainable fuel supply - each offering unique economic benefits that can foster community resilience and environmental sustainability. Woodlands **support local food economies** and enhance food security by providing a natural source of food products. Additionally, they **attract tourism** through recreational activities and ecotourism, generating income for rural areas. Finally, woodlands contribute to a **sustainable energy supply** by providing renewable fuel sources in the form of wood. These diverse economic contributions demonstrate the significant value of maintaining and managing healthy woodlands for long-term prosperity.

Foraging activities, such as picking berries, gathering mushrooms or collecting herbs, are deeply intertwined with woodland biodiversity and ecosystem functioning. These practices contribute to ecosystem health by **maintaining species balance and supporting nutrient cycles**. Foraging in the UK has deep historical roots, dating back to ancient times when communities relied on gathering wild plants, fruits, nuts and fungi for sustenance. In medieval Britain, foraging was a crucial part of rural life, with people collecting wild herbs and berries to supplement their diets and use plants for **medicinal purposes**.

DID YOU KNOW ?

Autumn is the best time for gathering wild mushrooms, with over 15,000 species in the UK (**not all are edible!**) Some popular edible varieties include chanterelles, porcini, and field mushrooms.

However, **caution is essential while foraging**, as some mushrooms resemble poisonous varieties. Identification skills are crucial for a safe (and tasty) foraging experience.

For humans, foraging offers more than just food; it provides an **opportunity to reconnect with nature**, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation of natural resources. Foraging encourages sustainable practices and promotes environmental stewardship, as people who regularly forage often develop a stronger attachment to the landscapes they depend on. This **connection can inspire individuals and communities to preserve and protect these ecosystems**.

In addition to its environmental impact, foraging contributes to wellbeing by promoting healthy lifestyles and offering economic opportunities. Locally sourced, wild foods can become integrated into the **sustainable food economy**, reducing food miles and strengthening the connection between people and their local environment. Moreover, foraging activities support mental and physical health by encouraging outdoor activities, reducing stress, and fostering a sense of mindfulness and presence in nature. It is worth reflecting that thought needs to be given to the sustainability of commercial foraging on a case-by-case basis.

18 Tourism and recreation

Woodland tourism encompasses diverse activities capitalising on forested areas' inherent beauty and cultural significance. These activities include hiking, birdwatching, camping, and learning about local wildlife. Woodland tourism offers many benefits, such as providing recreational spaces for visitors and opportunities for learning about the environment. Economically, it **creates jobs** and supports local businesses while promoting woodland area protection and sustainable use.

Woodland tourism can be developed as ecotourism, a specific tourism approach that directly benefits local communities while fostering the conservation of natural habitats. It provides income through activities like **guided tours, local crafts, and hospitality services** while **encouraging the conservation** of natural habitats. Ecotourism also plays an essential role in preserving cultural heritage by encouraging respect for historical landmarks and traditional practices, often tied to forested areas. This form of tourism, therefore, not only **supports the environment** but also strengthens community ties to their land and cultural history.

The Old Wood of Drum

Incorporating **children's crafts** into woodland tourism allows children to engage creatively with nature by making items like leaf prints, pinecone animals, or twig-based sculptures. This is an example of a hands-on activity that enhances their connection to the environment while promoting learning about local ecosystems. Additionally, it **offers a fun, family-friendly** way to support sustainable tourism and local communities.

Is your woodland family-friendly?

Woodlands can provide local communities with fuel, helping to reduce reliance on costly energy sources. They offer a renewable **source for heating**, contributing to local energy security and economic development. Sustainable wood harvesting from community woodlands can help address fuel poverty, particularly in rural areas due to **rising energy costs**. This can provide an affordable heating option, increasing energy security for vulnerable populations. **Sustainable practices**, such as selective logging and coppicing, help maintain the health of the woodland ecosystem.

These practices ensure that woodlands continue regenerating and storing carbon while supporting biodiversity. As **energy prices rise**, the demand for wood as a sustainable **energy source is expected to grow**. By adopting sustainable harvesting methods, communities can secure a **long-term wood supply** while safeguarding the environment.

This fosters local economic opportunities and resilience against energy shocks, making sustainable wood harvesting a crucial part of **addressing fuel poverty in the future**.

Conclusion

Woodlands provide benefits that enrich the lives of individuals, communities, and the environment. This guide illustrates that there is more to woodlands than nature; it is essential to people's and communities' wellbeing, happiness, and health. Embedded in ecological, social, and economic dimensions, nature-based solutions tackle pressing environmental problems globally, like climate change or biodiversity loss, and at local scales by improving resilience and social cohesion.

Communities that contribute to woodland management initiatives receive a wide array of benefits. These benefits range from improved mental and physical health, enhanced opportunities for social interaction and strengthened cultural heritage to increased economic opportunities through sustainable fuel supply, tourism, and food provisioning. Woodlands' ability to regulate microclimates, improve air quality, and reduce noise pollution also emphasises their significant role in safeguarding the environment and enhancing the quality of life.

This guide underscores the importance of inclusive and participatory approaches in managing communal woodlands. Empowering local communities to **participate in decision-making** and stewardship fosters a sense of belonging, ownership, and responsibility. Such engagement ensures the sustainability of these projects and helps address equity, justice and inclusion, ensuring that all share the benefits of nature.

Rather than solely extracting resources and benefits, **caring for woodlands** is pivotal in creating sustainable, long-term ecosystems and is at the core of effective nature-based solutions. When managed responsibly, these woodlands can continue **providing ecosystem services indefinitely**. Caring for woodlands becomes invaluable because instead of solely extracting resources, it ensures that healthy ecosystems are maintained for future generations.

If managed well, these woodlands could continue to provide many ecosystem services. Most importantly, restoration and conservation of woodlands pave the way towards developing **thriving ecosystems that benefit both humans and nature**.

Glossary

Aesthetic appreciation: Recognition of natural landscapes' beauty fosters human enjoyment and wellbeing.

Biodiversity: The variety of animal and plant life in a particular habitat or ecosystem which is crucial for ecosystem health and resilience.

Coppicing: A woodland management technique whereby trees are periodically cut down to ground level to stimulate regrowth from the tree base.

Cultural services: The intangible benefits that individuals derive from the natural world, including recreational activities, aesthetic enjoyment and spiritual enrichment.

Ecotourism: The practice of responsible travel to natural environments that aims to conserve ecological integrity and enhance the welfare of local communities. An important aspect of ecotourism is the involvement of interpretation and education.

Ecosystem services: The benefits people receive from ecosystems, including provisioning, regulating, supporting, and cultural services.

Forest therapy: The practice of spending time in forested areas for mental and physical wellbeing.

Foraging: The practice of gathering edible food items from nature, such as berries, mushrooms and herbs.

Geolocation: The process of determining the geographical position of a human address or technology in the form of longitude and latitude.

Green Infrastructure: A strategically planned network of natural and semi-natural spaces designed to deliver ecosystem services.

Green Spaces: Natural or semi-natural areas that provide ecological, social, and recreational benefits by integrating vegetation, open spaces, and biodiversity into human environments. Usually passive in function, primarily serving as leisure spaces.

Inclusion: Ensuring that all members of society feel valued, respected and included regardless of their background or identity.

Microclimate regulation: The process of managing the climate of a specific area to create favourable conditions.

Nature-based solutions: Actions or strategies that leverage natural processes to address societal challenges such as climate change and biodiversity loss.

Nature awareness: The comprehension and appreciation of the natural environment, cultivating a profound connection between humanity and its surroundings.

Participatory projects: Initiatives that engage community members in the decision-making process and practical activities, thereby promoting a sense of local ownership.

Provisioning services: Ecosystem services that provide direct products like food, water, and raw materials.

Renewable energy: Energy from replenished natural sources, such as wood harvesting from sustainably managed forests.

Resilience: The capacity of ecosystems or communities to recuperate from disturbances or distress, including impacts attributable to climate change.

Social cohesion: The degree of connectedness and solidarity between groups in a society, fostering a sense of belonging and shared purpose.

Spiritual wellbeing: A sense of inner peace and connection to something greater than oneself.

Sustainable fuel supply: Energy sources derived from renewable natural resources, such as sustainably harvested wood, used for heating and other purposes.

Sustainable harvesting: The practice of extracting natural resources to ensure they can regenerate and are not depleted.

Trail camera: A discreet camera that can be left outside to capture images of wildlife activity for monitoring and research.

Woodland management: The stewardship of forested regions to preserve ecological, social, and economic benefits.

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Disclaimer

This guide is intended only to provide inspiration and illustrative examples. It represents our current understanding and is based on a systematic literature review at the time of writing. While every effort has been made to ensure its accuracy and reliability, the authors cannot accept responsibility or liability for any decisions, actions, or outcomes arising from using or applying the information provided in this guide. Please note that the examples provided in this guide are not an exhaustive list; they are intended solely for informational purposes and do not constitute a financial promotion or provide investment advice, recommendations, advice, or endorsements. Users are encouraged to seek professional advice or conduct further research before acting on the insights provided.

Appendix: Useful weblinks and resources

Organisations and Initiatives Supporting Forestry, Conservation, and Sustainable Land Use

Institution name	Description	Website address
ANCIENT TREE FORUM	Promotes the value and protection of ancient trees and other veteran trees across the UK.	www.ancienttreeforum.org.uk
ARBORICULTURAL ASSOCIATION	A professional organisation for tree care professionals on all matters arboricultural in the UK.	www.trees.org.uk
BUGLIFE	A charity dedicated to the conservation of invertebrates, promoting habitat restoration and biodiversity.	www.buglife.org.uk
BIOFUELWATCH	Provides information and undertakes advocacy and campaigning concerning the climate, biodiversity, land and human rights and public health impacts of large-scale industrial bioenergy	www.biofuelwatch.org.uk
CAMPAIGN TO PROTECT RURAL ENGLAND	An organisation dedicated to promoting, enhancing, and protecting England's countryside	www.cpre.org.uk
COMMUNITY WOOD RECYCLING	A social enterprise focused on repurposing wood waste for environmental and social benefits.	www.communitywoodrecycling.org.uk
COMMUNITY WOODLANDS ASSOCIATION	Supports community woodland groups in Scotland.	www.communitywoods.org
CONFOR	Supports sustainable forestry and wood-using businesses through political engagement and market promotion.	www.confor.org.uk
FOREST STEWARDSHIP COUNCIL UK	Aims to promote responsible forest management through certification of sustainably sourced timber products.	www.fsc-uk.org
FOREST RESEARCH	The research agency of the Forestry Commission.	www.forestresearch.gov.uk
FORESTRY ENGLAND	Government agency managing public forests across England.	www.forestryengland.uk
GREENSPACE SCOTLAND	An organisation that supports the sustainable development of green spaces in Scotland.	www.greenspacescotland.org.uk

GROUNDWORK UK	A charity that works to improve local communities through environmental and social initiatives.	www.groundwork.org.uk
INSTITUTE OF CHARTERED FORESTERS	The UK's professional body for foresters and arboriculturists.	www.charteredforesters.org
JOHN MUIR TRUST	Dedicated to the conservation and preservation of wild places in the UK.	www.johnmuirtrust.org
NATIONAL TRUST	Charity preserving historic sites and landscapes across the UK.	www.nationaltrust.org.uk
NATURAL ENGLAND	A government body responsible for protecting and enhancing England's natural environment.	LINK
NATIONAL FOREST COMPANY	Manages the National Forest in central England.	www.nationalforest.org
NATIONAL TRUST FOR SCOTLAND	Manages historic sites and natural landscapes in Scotland.	www.nts.org.uk
NATURAL RESOURCES WALES	A principal environmental regulatory and advisory body for Wales, it oversees the sustainable management of its natural resources.	naturalresources.wales
PROGRAMME FOR THE ENDORSEMENT OF FOREST CERTIFICATION	Supports sustainable forest management certification in the UK.	www.pefc.co.uk
RSPB	Royal Society for the Protection of Birds.	www.rspb.org.uk
ROYAL FORESTRY SOCIETY	Provides resources and education to promote the scientific, sustainable management of woodlands.	www.rfs.org.uk
SCOTLAND NATURE AGENCY (NATURESCOT)	Scotland's national nature agency is responsible for biodiversity conservation and sustainable land use.	www.nature.scot
SCOTTISH FORESTRY	A Scottish Government agency is responsible for forestry policy, support and regulations.	forestry.gov.scot
SMALL WOODS ASSOCIATION	Advocates for the sustainable management of small woodlands in the UK.	smallwoods.org.uk
THE TREE COUNCIL	A national charity that brings together individuals, organisations, and government bodies to promote the conservation and planting of trees.	treecouncil.org.uk
THE WILD NETWORK	Encourages outdoor learning and play for children, promoting engagement with natural woodlands.	www.thewildnetwork.com
TREES FOR CITIES	UK charity working nationally and internationally to improve lives by planting trees in cities.	www.treesforcities.org

TREES FOR LIFE	Works to rewild the Scottish Highlands through extensive tree-planting projects aimed at ecological restoration and biodiversity.	treesforlife.org.uk
WILDLIFE TRUSTS	Umbrella group for Wildlife Trusts in the UK. The purpose is to bring wildlife back, to empower people to take meaningful action for nature.	www.wildlifetrusts.org
WOODLAND HERITAGE	Charity works to support and fund research, education, and sustainable practices in British forestry, focusing on the health and resilience of woodlands.	woodlandheritage.org.uk
WOODLAND INITIATIVES NETWORK	Partnership network of local woodland groups across the UK aimed to promote community-led woodland management and conservation.	www.win.org.uk
WOODLAND SKILLS CENTRE	Organisation offering courses in traditional woodland management and sustainable forestry practices in North Wales.	woodlandskillscentre.uk
WOODLAND TRUST	Focused on protecting and restoring native woodlands for biodiversity and public benefit.	www.woodlandtrust.org.uk

Appendix: Recommended Reading

Community Woodlands Association Report:

Testing a framework to describe models of community woodland case studies: Six case studies of Scottish community woodlands. A report by the Community Woodlands Association on behalf of Forest Research.

This baseline study provides an overview of the current state of community woodlands in Scotland, Wales, and England, as well as an evidence review of community woodland governance for the Independent Panel on Forestry, combined with several workshops to share experiences and defined priorities. [Link: <https://bit.ly/WoodlandFramework>]

Initiatives and Networks Advancing Nature-Based Solutions and Urban Sustainability

Programs and repositories	Description	Website address
CONNECTING NATURE	Programme for the innovation and implementation of nature-based solutions.	www.connectingnature.eu
EUPOLIS	Nature-based solution interventions for open public spaces with citizens' needs for improved public health and wellbeing.	www.eupolis-project.eu
GROW GREEN	Climate and Water Resilience, Sustainable Economic Growth, Healthy Citizens and Environments.	www.growgreenproject.eu
INTERLACE	Project to strengthen urban ecosystem restoration in the European Union and Latin America.	www.interlace-project.eu
NABI	Nature-based innovations for Urban Forest and Rainwater Management.	LINK
NATURE4CITIES	Project supports national and local governments to accelerate climate action from cities by protecting and/or restoring ecosystem services.	LINK
NETWORK NATURE	Resource for the Nature-based Solutions community, creating local, regional and international cooperation opportunities.	www.networknature.eu
OPERANDUM	Tools and methods for demonstrating and market uptake of Nature-Based Solutions to reduce hydro-meteorological risks.	www.operandum-project.eu/nbs
OPPLA	Open platform provides a knowledge marketplace on natural capital, ecosystem services and nature-based solutions.	www.oppla.eu
PHUSICOS	Project demonstrates the effectiveness of nature-based solutions and their ability to reduce the impacts of small, frequent events in rural mountain landscapes.	www.phusicos.eu
RECONNECT	Project demonstrates, references and upscales Nature-based Solutions in rural and natural areas.	www.reconnect.eu
UNALAB	Project contributes to the development of smarter, more inclusive, more resilient and increasingly sustainable cities through the implementation of nature-based solutions	www.unalab.eu/en
URBAN GREENUP	Project developing, applying and validating a methodology for Renaturing Urban Plans to mitigate the effects of climate change, improve air quality and water management and increase the sustainability of our cities through innovative nature-based solutions.	www.urbangreenup.eu
URBAN NATURE ATLAS	Repository of nature-based solutions from European cities.	www.una.city
VARCITIES	Project about Nature-based Actions for Health, Wellbeing and Resilience in Cities.	www.varcities.eu

Appendix: How to use this guide for a participatory workshop

This guide contains useful information on community woodlands that can be used for participatory workshops to explore the benefits of community woodlands. The intention is to offer scenarios that enable community members to approach their woodlands and potential community projects in a new manner. Below are suggested guidelines for running a workshop about community benefits and steps for conducting a community-participatory workshop using this guide.

STEP 1: Understanding community woodland benefits

Explain briefly the general advantages the community can draw from spending time in woodlands and encourage workshop participants to share personal and community-based experiences.

STEP 2: Introducing reflection guidelines

Hand out and present the guide with 19 community benefits, giving participants discussion reference points.

STEP 3: Reflection in small groups

Form small groups and give each group a focus guideline. Each small group could examine community woodlands' benefits and associated constraints.

STEP 4: Group sharing and discussion

Each group presents their insights, focusing on identified benefits, challenges and ideas for improvement. Facilitate a broader discussion to find common themes and explore unique perspectives.

STEP 5: Action planning

Close with a final reflection in which each participant shares a key takeaway. The facilitator could liaise with the group to think about what duties are needed, establish dates, and determine procedures for post-event communication. This can help ensure that lessons learned during the workshop are implemented. Collect feedback to improve future workshops and encourage participants to stay engaged with the woodland project.

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